

Quo vadis? A controversial look at the Reformation

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ABSTRACT: The 500th anniversary of the Reformation is a positive event on many aspects of society in which not only the theological but also the social achievements of this powerful movement initiated by Dr. Martin Luther are especially highlighted. This study, however, aims at revising at the historical level the interaction between the positive attitude and one of denigration of the Reformation movement, present from the beginning to the present day. This relationship is mirrored throughout history, especially in the Catholic-Protestant discourse. The current positive dialogue on the Reformation event sometimes creates a mild impression on it. A glance behind the historical backdrops reveals a completely different reality: in the last 500 years, the Reformation movement and Luther as its initiator have suffered from a severe slander which consequences have been felt until now. Even though this tension will not dissolve in the future, however, Christianity still needs precisely this reform spirit to survive.

KEY WORDS: Reformation, Martin Luther, Counter-Reformation, Protestantism, Catholicism, Ecumenism

Doubt unites, beliefs divide. Inspired by this thought, the Reformation movement looks retrospectively on October 31, when it celebrates its 500th anniversary since its inception.

According to the testimony of Philipp Melanchthon, Luther's collaborator, who put the 95 theses on the gate of the Wittenberg church on October 31.¹ Although these were dedicated to theologians only, their news spread rapidly among the people, causing great interest among the simple people and craftsmen, but also among the cultured or erudite people, especially in the humanist circles. So, Albrecht Durer sent Luther a collection of wood engravings and sculptures in gratitude, while the poet Hans Sachs of Nuremberg called him "the Württemberg nightingale". The humanists Willibald Pirckheimer and Konrad Peutinger voiced their appreciation for the reformer's courage, and Erasmus-von Rotterdam—the top of the scholars—said Luther did two unutterable things: he put his hand first on the pope's crown and then on the belly of the monks, after he immediately sent the theses to his colleague Thomas Morus from England.

But the opposing camp did not take much time to form. Luther's direct enemy, the Dominican Johannes Tetzel, urged his conviction and execution: "*The heretic be thrown into the fire in three weeks and leave for the heavens on a pyre.*" A theologian from Eisenach wrote on the beginning of all Luther's theses, the Greek letter Theta, which begins the Greek word Thanatos, and meaning death. The literary opposition against Luther soon became active as well. Johannes Eck, one of the famous theologians of the time, talked of him as a heretic and a Hussite who behaved "uneducated and rebellious." If in the beginning many Reformation followers had enjoyed Erasmus's remark, many now supported the work of Thomas Murner's old belief work, entitled "*About the Great Lutheran Madman*" (1522), as well as the offenses of the ardent humanist Johannes Cochläus, who

named the reformer as being crazy or born of Satan, an alcoholic or a womanizer. (Because he got married even though he was a monk).

500 Years of Polemic: Luther between Slander, Debate and Interpretation

Catholic historian Adolf Herte tried to prove in a three-volume work (*Das katholische Lutherbild im Bann der Lutherkommentare des Cochläus, 1943*) that Luther's image until the modern era was marked by the discrediting of Cochläus. It soon turned out that the 95 theses were just a reason for discussion while the basic motivation was about salvation: How does a man become righteous before God? the teaching of salvation only through faith in the center discussion. For the Protestant side, the rediscovery of Paulinic teaching through Luther is the "Sanctuary of Reformation" (W. Dantine). The Catholic side, however, regarded it for almost half of millennium as a "Scandal" (J.B. Bossuet), "a transformation of Christ's salvation in madness" (J.A. Möhler), a "confusion of moral elemental terms" (M.J. Scheeben) and "a philosophy of nature" (H. Denifle). The man who spread such heresies in the world could not be other - from the perspective of the Jesuits - than an "Epicure's pig" and "the most disastrous monster on earth" (Beyna 1969, 13).

Still up to the 20th century, the reformer was considered in the Catholic circle as a "normal person" (H. Denifle) with an "abnormal character" (H. Grisar). Even there, where there was calmer and less aggressiveness - as in the world of art and philosophy - there were unilateral images that blurred the look of Luther and his Reformation, which is still the case today. The romantic-idealistic image of the Christian European Union of the Middle Ages (*republica christiana*) cannot accept until today that this so-called "unity" was destroyed by the Reformation movement because of a heroic loyalty to the truth. On the contrary, it is considered that

this rupture has brought about modern issues such as nationalism and racism, and then in a direct line - according to the poet Thomas Mann - from Luther to Hitler. (Loewenich 1970, 310).

The consideration for Luther outside confessional borders

At the inter-confessional level, there is a consensus that Luther's work involves, on the one hand, a unique, epochal event, and on the other hand, requires a critical perception. It is to be emphasized that Luther's reformation not only marked German thinking, culture and history but also the thinking of many other nations. So it cannot be denied that Luther marks a "crucial point of universal history" (G. Schramm). A modern and diverse Europe as today would not have been possible without Luther's Reformation. Heinz Schilling said: *"It was to some extent the tragic destiny of Luther, to initiate the intellectual, cultural and political differentiation of Europe and thus to open up a modern pluralist and liberal way ... So the religious link of the Christianity unity was Luther's life mission."* (Heinz 2013, 94).

Today, however, the religious piety, as well as Luther's intention for biblical reform, is appreciated even by the Roman Catholic Church when it is claimed that he was a religious man "homo religious" (J. Lortz) or even a "homo propheticus" (J. Hessen). The Reformer is regarded as "Father of Faith" (P. Manns), while his teaching of righteousness by faith is regarded as a "return to the gospel" (H. Küng) that claims to regain membership of "the birth right" (H.O. Pesch) inside the Catholic Church. Even though Luther's excommunication from Rome in 1521 was not canceled, in 1970 Cardinal Willenbrands - then the head of the Christian unity secretariat - spoke of Luther as a "common teacher of righteousness through faith." And Pope John Paul II emphasized—in the visit of

the Scandinavian countries in 1989—the profound religiosity of the reformer.

In the neo-protestant cults, however, he enjoys a broad appreciation. Through the Reformation, “the history of the evangelical family” was born, from which came a lot of extra movements, partly competitive but also contradictory, which - from their own perspective - rely more or less on the heritage of the Reformation. (It must be borne in mind that the Reformation later produced until now more than 30,000 confessions and denominations). This history of the evangelical family has already begun before Luther, Zwingli, Calvin, or Wycliffe. Because the reforming spark and the predecessors of the Reformation have their origins in the Waldenses in the 14th century Italy, the Lolarzs in the 15th century England and J. Hus in the Bohemian Reformation. The road of this history was subjected to both intolerance and persecution, but in turn it responded in the same manner. In this context, it must be mentioned Luther’s attitude towards baptism seekers or the evangelical church’s reaction to modern neo-protestant churches or the missionary movements of the 20th century, which intends to continue and complete the Reformation inheritance. (Fleischmann-Bisten 2014, 188-190).

And within the Adventist Church, Luther’s reformation was viewed and highlighted from the beginning as the work of God. Such as from the Adventist point of view of the understanding of history, the Reformation work was not only regarded as a historical event but as a divine intervention through Luther in order to bring Christianity back to the essence of Gospel and Bible teaching, to the Word of God and not to tradition. As the (neo) Protestant Church, the Adventist Church fully supports the reform creed: *Sola scriptura* (only the Holy Scriptures as the source of faith), *Solo Cristo* (only Jesus Christ as the Savior), *Sola Gratia* (only grace as a means of salvation), and *Sola Fide* (only faith as a means of receiving grace). Thus Ellen G. White — as the founder of the Seventh-day Adventist

Church - mentioned Luther at least 400 times, more than any other Reformation leader. Adventist theologians and historians have often indicated the importance of Luther's work as the foundation of the restoration movement of biblical truth. Thus for Ludwig R. Conradi the teachings of the book of Daniel and Revelation were "a loud testimony" against the decadence of the papal church. LeRoy E. Froom describes Luther in the four volumes entitled *The Prophetic Faith of Our Father* (1954) as a "genius of the Reformation."

The discovery of the Reformation - of forgiveness and righteousness only through Christ, and only by faith via-a-vis the recognition of the deformation of the medieval church - is to Froom a climax in church history, impossible to separate from Luther's person. The contribution of historian Daniel Walther, who has been particularly concerned with the theological relationship between Luther and the Seventh-day Adventist Church, must be highlighted. (Walther 1991, 9-11). He concludes that the following theological concepts continue and mark the reforming mandate of this church: the universal priesthood, the Bible as the norm of faith, righteousness by faith, the expectation of the return of Christ, and partly the teaching about the state of man in death as well as about the Antichrist.

Walter Eberhardt recalls Luther's work in "*Reformation and Counterreformation*" (1973) that it was not his work, but "*behind the great awakening of the Reformation days was a strong person.*" (Eberhardt 1973, 39). This statement summarizes how the Seventh-day Adventist Church thinks about Luther and his work. At the same time, it is emphasized that Luther's movement does not entirely represent Reformation. Because neither the meaning of Zwingli's or Calvin's work should be neglected. On the other hand, Zwingli's sacramental critique or Calvin's teaching about the Law and the Holy Supper left as many traces in the Adventist thinking.

Reformation from an ecumenical perspective

The renunciation of polemic and slander between confessions began with the advent of the ecumenical movement. The moment of a positive appreciation of the Reformation by the Roman Catholic Church followed after the Second World War through the work of Joseph Lortz "Reformation in Germany" (Bd. 1, 1939/40). He proposed a new perspective of inter-confessional approach, in which there is no emphasis on the religious divide, but on the positive reforming character. From a historic point of view, the author renounced the intentional evil denigration and appreciated Luther as "homo religious." At the same time, he admitted that the reformer's criticism of the church at that time was indeed justified. However, since the 16th century Catholicism only represented a denatured image of it, the reformer fought an image of the church that was not actually Catholic. (Lortz 1939/40, 176). Through these statements, modern Christianity has distanced itself from the lack of understanding and Catholic will from previous centuries and has adopted a change in Catholic research of the Reformation - as Evangelical historian Heinrich Bornkamm notes.

Joseph Lortz's contemporary Johannes Hessen took one step further, making his first attempt to integrate the image of the reformer into Catholic thinking. In his book "Luther From a Catholic Perspective" (1947), he not only designated Luther as a "homo religious", but also "homo propheticus". From this perspective, Luther built further on the basis and according to Christian Catholic values. (Jedin 1966, 79–101). By the Second Council of the Vatican (1962-1965), whereby the Catholic Church joined the ecumenical movement, this positive trend developed further. Even though the Council did not make any statements about the reformers themselves, members of the reforming churches were approached as "separated brothers", (Beinert 2010, the term is already found

with Augustinus (354-430) who through it appointed the Donatist schismatics) who in turn also seek God in the Holy Scriptures. The Vatican Council used the term “Reformation” (Ebd.) and regretted —without condemnation— the religious separations that emerged as a consequence. In the period that followed the Catholic researchers of the Reformation surprised by amazing positions and findings. For Luther was not only appreciated as a “Catholic opportunity” (H.O. Pesch) but also as a “Catholic necessity” within the Reformation (A. Brandenburg). In the Second Vatican Council, Luther received a chance and was going to receive further an appropriate place in the Catholic Church, for he is no longer a “heretic” but a “father of faith” (P. Manns). (Heinz 1988, 253–265)

In light of this positive opening, the conservative Catholic reactions did not remain silent. After the council came various publications that called Luther a “subjectivist” and a “destroyer of the church.” (Kötting 1982, 30–35). Such initiatives, which led to a regression after Joseph Lortz’s interpretation, have often found the approval of distinguished church figures such as Cardinals Hans Urs von Balthasar and Joseph Ratzinger. So it is no surprise that the reformer remained in the tradition of Pius brothers further disqualified as a false prophet (Materialdienst der Evangelischen Zentralstelle für Weltanschauungsfragen 1995, 84).

Luther and the Reformation: Official Perspective of the Roman Catholic Church

Despite many positive reactions to the Reformation and reformers coming from Catholic theologians and historians, the final question remains: what is the official position of the Vatican regarding this debate? And here - a look at the historical backstage is very helpful. Already the Edict of Worms (1521)—released by the papal legate

Aleander—reproached the reformer that he is possessed by an “evil spirit” and embodies the “evil enemy” in human form. The Council of Trent (1545-1563) has intentionally not mentioned the names of the reformers for them to have the sentence of forgetfulness (*Damnatio memoriae*). But by the phrase: “*Heretics, who in tumultuous times preached in the struggle against the Catholic Church*” (Denzinger and Hünemann 1991, §1533) the Council referred to the reformers consciously giving up on them.

During the Counter-Reformation period, Pope Urban VIII condemned the Hussites in 1627, Wycliffe’s descendants, Lutherans and Calvinists, as well as pirates or thieves. And in 1910 Pope Pius X in the encyclical *Editae Sapeden* has admonished Protestantism as the first step towards atheism and the destruction of religion. In 1925, the German counter-reformer, the Jesuit Petrus Canisius, was declared a saint. He was especially appreciated as the one who dared to face the “monster Luther”, as well as the one who saved the German culture. A lot of other canons of counter-reforming personalities - such as Roberto Bellarmin by Pope Pius XI, Anthony von Padua by Pope Pius XII or Laurentius von Brindisi by Pope John XXIII - at the dawn of the 2nd The Vatican Council surprised quite a few ecumenists from the church.

But what disturbs the Curia of Rome most about Luther is his refusal to receive salvation through the Catholic Church, implicitly the refusal of papal authority. In 1960 Bishop Pietro Parente presented this refusal as “the distortion of the work of salvation through Luther.” This conflict still continues. In 2011, the Bishop of Regensburg, the current prefect of the congregation, Gerhard Ludwig Müller, categorically called for the distancing of the Protestant world from Luther’s anti-Christ’s statements, which would have no place in the context of an ecumenical dialogue. The Vatican is willing today—as Pope John Paul II already said in 1980 during a visit to Germany—to see in Luther if not a “discoverer of

salvation” at least one “seeker of salvation.” Through this formulation, the reformer would fit his teaching about the salvation through faith of both Protestants and Catholics. By means of the joint statement on the teaching of salvation through faith in 1999 of the Lutheran Federation and the Catholic Council to promote Christian unity, where consensus has been established on the basis of biblical truths—Willenbrands’ vision seems to have come true. But is Luther really rehabilitated by this, and the chasm created by the reformation within Christianity is totally outdated?

For Pope Benedict XVI, this consensus means an important step towards the path of Christian unity: Protestants are getting closer to Catholic teaching. For others, like, for example, the Protestant Reinhard Frieling, this statement is, on the contrary, an obstacle to ecumenism. Indeed, Luther is not only a peripheral reminder, but the basic content of the salvation theory is formulated in the same way by the two churches, however, it is differently understood.

The Reformation goes on

Will the 500th anniversary of the Reformation of 2017 really lead to a turning point near the two great Christian confessions? At the moment, only assumptions can be made. Even though the modern era has determined the Protestant Church, even the Catholic Church to tolerance, fundamental points still remain under discussion, such as the official church or community of believers, sacramental baptism of newborns or mature baptism?

Heinrich Bedford-Strohm, president of the German Evangelical Church Council, wants the Reformation anniversary to become a “great celebration of Christ” to “spread an ecumenical spirit.” But the direction of the ecumenical vision is not clear. Cardinal Walter Kasper summarizes: “We have agreed that we want unity, but we

do not have a consensus on what unity should be, and in what direction the ecumenical path must lead.” (Kasper, 2016, 54f) One thing can certainly be said about Luther: The Catholic Church under the leadership of the Vatican will certainly not be able to confirm and fully support the basic theme of the Reformation of salvation through faith, of the direct relationship between man and God, and thus the denial of the need for church intercession in the process of salvation. The claim of the reform remains further on: *Causa Reformationis non est causa finita!* According to Luther’s understanding, the path of faith goes further in faithfulness to the gospel and to the living expectation of the return of Christ.

The same view is shared by the evangelical theologian Karl Barth who, in the final volume of “Church Dogmatics,” presents very clearly the relationship between Luther and the Reformed / Protestant official church. Christianity now has only one chance in regaining credibility and missionary power: only if it returns to personal Christianity. Because Martin Luther’s work is not over. The present world needs not Christians registered in the church registers, but convinced Christians who have the courage to testify for what they believe in and live their faith in practical life.

Notes

¹ The authenticity of the display of Luther’s theses at the gate of the church is questionable. A copy came undoubtedly to Archbishop Albrecht de Mainz, who at the same time was Archbishop of Magdeburg, thus responsible for Wittenberg. Other copies came to other religious personalities and one of them - as a reaction to the widespread ideas - to the indulgents seller, Johann Tetzel, who did not give Luther any answer. But without his consent a public discussion would have been perceived as a massive challenge. It is unlikely that Luther would have intended this or would not have been aware of it. The display of theses is first mentioned by the secretary of Luther Georg Rörer, who remembers in 1544 in a New Testament note

about the presentation of the theses at the gate of several churches in Wittenberg: "On the evening before the Feast of All Saints in the year 1517 Dr. Martin Luther pinned the theories about indulgences on the gates of the Wittenberg churches." (The original Latin text: "Anno Domini 1517 in profesto omnium Sanctorum. Witemberge in values templorum propositae sunt propositiones de Indulgentiis a Doctore Martino Luthero"). This little document found in 2006 reveals that the theses were presented to several churches in Wittenberg at the same time. However, its confirmatory value is controversial. (W. Marchewka, M. Schwibbe, A. Stephainski: *Zeitreise, 800 Jahre Leben in Wittenberg/Luther, 500 Jahre Reformation*, Edition Zeit Reise, Göttingen 2008, S. 39.) On the other hand, Rörer is unlikely to have witnessed the display of the theses. (Martin Treu: *An den Türen der Wittenberger Kirchen — Neues zur Debatte um den Thesenanschlag*).

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